

Turbine missile impact: empirical and numerical solutions

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Abstract

A study of the structural damage produced by turbine missiles to reinforced concrete walls has been conducted for an overvelocity test turbine cell. Literature formulas for assessing the structural resistance to perforation of containments have been compared and reviewed with respect to their applicability to the impact of massive rotor fragments. Finite difference computer simulations have been successfully applied and retained as a valuable support for the design of reinforced concrete structures against turbine missiles.

1 Introduction

The impact of fragments of turbine rotors against reinforced concrete walls has been considered in the past by nuclear power plant designers to provide adequate protection to specific plant components. This loading is also of primary importance in the design of the containment wall of cells used to test turbine rotor. The fragments of rotors can be massive, irregularly shaped and, can possess ejection velocities over 250 m/s, thus representing a potential cause of damage to the structural housing.

Empirical formulations derived from full-scale and scaled impact models have been used in the past to predict perforation of reinforced concrete walls by small projectiles. This methodology has been proved to be inadequate to predict wall perforation due to large fragments. In the last decade experimental data have been used to modify design formulas for the penetration of larger missiles, taking also into account the effect of steel reinforcement and liner plates.

A missile impact results on local effects and overall dynamic response of the walls and the supporting structures. Local effects due to impact of hard missiles include perforation, penetration or spalling depending on strength of concrete and steel reinforcement amount, contact area of the missile and impact energy, etc. This paper focuses on local effects associated to a perforation scenario. Optimal reinforcement and wall thickness have been found by means of empirical formulas and by the numerical simulations, as described in the following paragraphs.

2 Configuration of the Scenario

2.1 Cell structure geometry

The structural geometry of the test housing is represented by a cylindrical reinforced concrete wall with internal radius of 4.125 m (Figure 1). Reinforcement consists of an inner cylindrical plate of 2.2 centimeters able to sustain pressure related to internal vacuum conditions and a steel reinforcement on the outer side.

2.2 Missile geometry

The most severe scenario consists in the rupture of a 120° circular sector of the turbine rotor (Figure 1) weighting 11,130 Kg and impacting the wall with a velocity of 205 m/sec. The translational energy of a blunt impact normal to the wall has been considered.

3 Empirical Solutions

Practical design consists in preventing perforation by hard missiles. In literature different empirical formulas have been derived to evaluate minimum perforation velocities for concrete barriers, e.g. those proposed by Petri, the National Defence Research Committee (NDRC), CEA-EDF, Kennedy, Degen and Chang. They were developed on the basis of test data of cylindrical or ballistic projectiles whose shape and dimension differ from those of turbine missiles. None of these formulas directly quantified the influence of steel reinforcement.

Improved formulas have been derived to match available test results of turbine rotor fragment impacts conducted at full and reduced scale. They account for a steel plate fixed at the outer surface of the wall; see Degen, Kennedy and CEA-EDF methods [1]. In the improved formulas, the impact diameter d_p of a circle of equal perimeter to that of the missile impact region was used. Predictions of the perforation of a 40 MPa cubic compressive strength concrete wall with an outer plate of 1 centimeter are plotted in Figure 2 for the given impact scenario; the wall thickness for missile velocity of 205 m/sec ranges between 1.55 to 2.75 meters. Spreading of results increases for higher values of the impact velocity.

The Comité International du Béton [2], on the basis of modifications of the CEA-EDF method suggested by different authors, has recommended a formula which includes the influence of symmetrical steel reinforcement and of a steel plate at the outer side of the wall. This formula, which fits drop test results conducted in Europe, furnishes the minimum perforation velocity as:

$$V_p = 1.3 \rho^{1/6} f'_{c_{cyl}}{}^{1/2} \left[\frac{pe^2}{\pi m} \right]^{2/3} (B + 0.3)^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

being:

ρ = concrete density (Kg/m³);

$f'_{c_{cyl}}$ = characteristic compressive strength of concrete measured on cylindrical specimens (Pa);

p = perimeter of the impact area of the missile (m);

m = missile mass (Kg);

$B = B_1 + B_2$ = percentage of reinforcement given by:

$B_1 = 100 \frac{a}{ec}$ (bars reinforcement term, percent)

$B_2 = 100 \frac{S_{out}}{e}$ (outer steel plate term, percent)

where:

a = area of rebars;

e = concrete wall thickness;

c = spacing between rebars;

S_{out} = outer steel plate thickness.

Validity of the Equation (1) is restricted in the following ranges:

$$45 < V_p < 300$$

$$15 \cdot 10^6 < f'_{c_{cyl}} < 37 \cdot 10^6$$

$$0 < B_1 < 0.7$$

$$0 < B_2 < 4.3$$

$$0.2 < \frac{p}{\pi e} < 3$$

$$150 < \frac{m}{p^2 e} < 10^4$$

(2)

In the tests, reinforcement was provided by steel bars located in the two orthogonal directions on both faces of the concrete wall.

When a steel plate is also placed on the impacted face, the total energy needed to perforate the structural system should equal, at equilibrium condition, the kinetic energy of the missile:

$$\frac{1}{2} m V_M^2 = f_{yt} p S_{in}^2 + \frac{1}{2} m \left\{ 1.3 \rho^{1/6} f_{cyl}^{1/2} \left[\frac{p e^2}{\pi m} \right]^{2/3} \left[\left(\frac{a}{e c} + \frac{S_{out}}{e} \right) 100 + 0.3 \right]^{1/2} \right\}^2 \quad (3)$$

being:

V_M = missile velocity (m/sec);

S_{in} = thickness of the inner plate, (m);

f_{yt} = maximum shear strength of the inner plate (Pa).

A plot of the wall thickness vulnerable to perforation has been derived for the given impact scenario by varying the ratio S_{in}/S_{tot} , being $S_{tot} = S_{in} + S_{out}$, in Equation (3) and assuming only inner and outer steel plates. The vulnerability plot, reported in Figure 3 for different values of S_{tot} ranging from 1 to 10 centimeters, accounts for possible design configurations being $S_{in}/S_{tot} = 0$ the case with only the outer steel plate, and $S_{in}/S_{tot} = 1$ the case when only the inner steel plate is provided. It is noted that the shaded area in Figure 3 is outside the range of experimental test results.

From the vulnerability plot, it results that the inner plate marginally increases the wall resistance, given its reduced shear capacity in punching. The major effect on resistance is instead provided by the outer plate, i.e. when S_{in}/S_{tot} decreases to 0. The solution selected in terms of economy and installation, is represented by a concrete thickness of 2.1 meters for a S_{in}/S_{tot} ratio of 0.69. The reinforcement is composed by an inner steel plate of 2.2 centimeters thickness and by an outer steel plate of 1 centimeter (point 1 of Figure 3). For constructive reasons, the outer plate is replaced by steel bars of 32 millimeter at 8 centimeter in the two orthogonal directions.

Given the small influence of the inner steel plate, the above result can be compared to those of Figure 2; the point falls in the middle of the scatter range of the improved formula predictions.

4 Numerical Solution

The design of structural members subjected to rapidly applied loading can be substantially influenced by the nonlinear material behavior captured in the numerical simulations. Realistic constitutive laws and proper failure criteria are required for such a problem. To this purpose numerical analyses have been developed by means of the Autodyn 2D, a well known hydrocode suited to model of impact, penetration, blast and explosion events [3].

4.1 Structural modeling

The axisymmetric model is shown in Figure 4; target and missile have been idealised by Lagrangian processors. Total mass and curvature of the impacting surface of the missile were retained in the model. Inner and outer plates have been modeled by Lagrangian shells. The concrete mesh resulted in a 10x10

centimeters grid in the impacted area. Expected minimum time step was 0.015 msec.

4.2 Material modeling

4.2.1 Concrete Concrete material behavior requires the definition of the equation of state that defines the degree of material compaction in terms of pressure/volumetric strain relation and a strength model which describes the mode of failure due to shear, compaction and cracking. Porous equation of state and Mohr-Coulomb strength model have been used to characterise concrete under impact pressure loading. For two-dimensional stress wave propagation, it is usually the tensile behavior that ultimately determines the collapse of a structure: a tensile pressure cut-off is commonly used to model spalling of concrete. Static triaxial properties of a 70 MPa compressive strength concrete have been used to account for strain rate effects. Additionally, the tensile cut-off was modified to account for the higher resistance to conic plug formation provided by stirrups.

4.2.2 Steel Steel behavior has been modeled by means of linear equation of state for reinforcement steel and shock equation of state for missile steel. Strain rate dependency has been set according to Johnson and Cook model [4] which furnishes the Von Mises yield stress Y as:

$$Y = \left[A + B(\epsilon_p)^n \right] \left[1 + C \ln \dot{\epsilon}_p \right] \left[1 - T_{\text{hom}} \right] \quad (4)$$

being A , B , C , and n the material constants, ϵ_p and $\dot{\epsilon}_p$ the equivalent plastic strain and the normalized equivalent plastic strain rate (dimensionless) and T_{hom} the homologous temperature.

A failure criterion based on the cumulated equivalent plastic strain ϵ_p has been adopted. Experimental limits on the equivalent plastic strain at failure are rarely available. A numerical simulation of a uniaxial test specimen subjected to a constant extension velocity giving a desired strain rate has been developed. The engineering strain in terms of percentile elongation at failure was used to determine the equivalent plastic strain value over which steel capacity is smeared. The ultimate strain used in this study was 90%.

4.3 Numerical Analyses

Four cases are presented (see Figure 4). The first case models the selected design configuration. Cases 2 and 3 represent sensitivity analyses of the design configuration based upon increasing outer and inner reinforcement amount, respectively. Numerical case 4 models a thin concrete wall with higher reinforcement ratio. Main material properties used through the analyses are reported in Table 1. Missile velocities and equivalent plastic strains are presented in Figure 5.

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4.3.1 Numerical Case 1 Analyses indicated local severe damage at 10 msec. The outer steel plate failed while concrete fractured in a region with radius in excess of 1.5 meters. Inner steel plate entered the plastic zone, missile and structural parts showed a low residual velocity. This situation describes an incipient perforation.

4.3.2 Numerical Case 2 The outer steel plate was increased to 5 centimeters to provide better resistance. Results do not show this trend, thus indicating that this problem is driven by mass properties. Outer steel reached failure and the inner plate presented a minor extent of plastic behavior. This configuration is represented by point 2A in Figure 3; the wall thickness of 2.1 meters is larger than the minimum thickness of 1 meter given by the vulnerability plot (point 2B).

4.3.3 Numerical Case 3 An increase to 5 centimeters of the inner steel plate with respect to Case 1 did not substantially affect results. This confirms the minor contribution of the inner steel plate.

4.3.4 Numerical Case 4 Structural parameters indicated that the wall cannot absorb the impact loading. Missile residual velocity after the impact was about 60 m/sec.

4.3.5 Discussion of the numerical results Results of Case 1 are in agreement with the vulnerability plot (point 1). Cases 2 and 3 show that increasing reinforcement, residual velocities do not vary substantially; the response is driven by mass properties. Points 2B and 4 show that a significant reduction in wall thickness will imply perforation; they fall in the dashed zone of Figure 3, out of the range of validity of CEB recommendations.

5 Conclusion

Perforation of the reinforced concrete housing of an overvelocity turbine test facility due to an internal generated massive missile has been studied. Review of the literature formulas for assessing the structural resistance to perforation has revealed a large scatter in terms of the minimum required wall thickness. A vulnerability plot for practical design of the reinforced concrete section has been built on the basis of CEB recommendations for the given impact scenario. Results of numerical simulations indicated that the validity range of the vulnerability plot is probably overestimated for the given impact scenario.

References

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3. Century Dynamics, *AUTODYN-2D, User's Manual*, 1989.
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Table 1 Material property constants

CONCRETE SUBGRID		
Maximum yielding stress Y_{max}	330 MPa	Equation of state: Porous Strength model: Mohr-Coulomb
Yielding curve slope	0.9	
Tensile cut-off	-16.1 MPa	
INNER STEEL SHELL		
Yield strength	355 MPa	Equation of state: Linear Strength model: Johnson and Cook
Hardening constant	275 MPa	
Hardening exponent	0.36	
Ultimate strain	0.9	
Erosion strain	2	
OUTER STEEL SHELL		
Yield strength	430 MPa	Equation of state: Linear Strength model: Johnson and Cook
Hardening constant	275 MPa	
Hardening exponent	0.36	
Ultimate strain	0.9	
Erosion strain	2	
STEEL MISSILE SUBGRID		
Yield strength	635 MPa	Equation of state: Shock Strength model: Johnson and Cook
Hardening constant	275 MPa	
Hardening exponent	0.36	
Ultimate strain	high value	
Erosion strain	high value	

Figure 1: Characteristics of the overvelocity test turbine structure and the turbine missile.

Figure 2 Prediction of minimum perforation velocity by empirical formulas for the given impact scenario

Figure 3: Vulnerability plot for the given impact scenario based on CEB recommendations

Figure 4: Numerical cases

CASE 1

CASE 2

CASE 3

CASE 4

Figure 5. Missile velocity and equivalent plastic strain time histories at relevant target points